

NFDI4Chem, Chemistry Consortium in the NFDI

NFDI4Chem Converter Service Infrastructure

TA4 – Metadata, Data Standards and Publication Standards

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Content

Executive Summary	3
Project Objectives	4
Detailed Report on the Deliverable	4
Description of Work	4
Adaptation of work plan	8
Next steps	8

Executive Summary

The integration of the latest analytical devices and technologies into chemistry labs, combined with a diverse array of existing instrumentation, expands the range of data formats and types researchers and data infrastructures have to deal with, as vendors of analytical instrumentation use their own formats to store measurement data. This introduces challenges on interoperability and might hamper reuse of data, especially when the raw data can only be processed and visualised with proprietary vendor software.

A converter service built on the Common Workflow Language (CWL) has been established, to effectively navigate these complexities and to implement robust mechanisms that ensure seamless conversion of diverse data formats into standardised forms. An infrastructure for deploying a converter service with attached but separated chemistry data type specific converters has been established, providing users with a streamlined, user-friendly platform for transforming data into standardised and open formats, as well as validation of the converted data obtained. The NFDI4Chem Converter Service, developed with Flask and compliant with the OpenAPI specification, provides a REST API for integration with NFDI4Chem services. Designed for ease of deployment, the service is packaged in a Docker image and includes a Helm chart for efficient deployment in Kubernetes environments. Currently, a converter for mass spectrometry data is available, also packed in a Docker image with Helm charts. There are plans to support additional data formats in future.

The source code of the Converter Service and the converter is available on GitHub under a permissive licence and docker images are available via Docker Hub to ease deployment. The NFDI4Chem Converter Service features a CI/CD pipeline for automating conversion and validation summary reports, promoting community collaboration.

Project Objectives

This deliverable has contributed particularly to **Objective 4.3** of TA4¹ to increase the adoption and integration of standards through generic software implementations. Moreover, this deliverable has contributed to the following key objectives of NFDI4Chem² :

Key Objective 3 to promote the use of digital tools in all stages of research by implementing Smart Laboratory Environments.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

Description of Work

The *NFDI4Chem Converter Service* is designed for multiple converters, each transforming data into a standardised format, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the *NFDI4Chem Converter Service (cs)* architecture. The NFDI4Chem Converter Service is a collection of one or more converters, each maintained in its own repository and designed to transform data into a standardised format via REST API.

¹ C. Steinbeck, O. Koepler, F. Bach, S. Herres-Pawlis, N. Jung, J. C. Liermann, S. Neumann, M. Razum, C. Baldauf, F. Biedermann, T. W. Bocklitz, F. Boehm, F. Broda, P. Czodrowski, T. Engel, M. G. Hicks, S. M. Kast, C. Kettner, W. Koch, G. Lanza, A. Link, R. A. Mata, W. E. Nagel, A. Porzel, N. Schlörer, T. Schulze, H.-G. Weinig, W. Wenzel, L. A. Wessjohann, S. Wulle, NFDI4Chem - Towards a National Research Data Infrastructure for Chemistry in Germany, *RIO* **2020**, 6, e55852, DOI: [10.3897/rio.6.e55852](https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.6.e55852), specifically see task T3.3.2 and T3.3.5

² Objectives - NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Chem, URL: <https://www.nfdi4chem.de/objectives/>.

NFDI4Chem Converter Service Infrastructure

Currently, the *NFDI4Chem Converter Service* has a converter to handle mass spectrometry data, but will be expanded with further converters e.g. for NMR spectroscopic data. Each converter module is developed using the Common Workflow Language³ (CWL), chosen for its outstanding interoperability, portability, and reproducibility. The source code of the *NFDI4Chem Converter Service* resides in a Git repository⁴, featuring a CI/CD pipeline, as shown in Figure 2.

The CI/CD pipeline automates the generation of comprehensive conversion and validation summary reports, as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 and also on GitHub⁵. Additionally, a snapshot of the conversion and validation CWL code is provided below the stages as illustrated in Figure 2.

³ Common Workflow Language, URL: <https://www.commonwl.org/>.

⁴ ms_converter, Lincoln Sherpa, GitLab RWTH-Aachen University, URL: https://git.rwth-aachen.de/linsherpa/ms_converter.

⁵ Converter Service Mass Spectrometry Converter, cs-ms-converter, NFDI4Chem, Github Repository, URL: <https://github.com/NFDI4Chem/cs-ms-converter>.

CWL Repository -1

Figure 2: Continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) Pipeline of the MS Converter Repository. CWL code snippets for conversion and validation are shown.

The conversion and validation reports provide an in-depth overview of the conversion and validation processes, ensuring transparency and testing across diverse file formats. Moreover, such reports may enhance community collaboration, as reports of failed conversion can be used to provide feedback to the developers of the underlying converters.

NFDI4Chem Converter Service Infrastructure

Figure 3: Summary report of the conversion step from MS Converter Repository *cs-ms-converter*⁴. One conversion failed because the MAT 95XP instrument is end-of-life and not all instrument configurations are fully supported by *msconvert*.

The repositories⁵ contain all the essential code required to operate a converter, which is built on Flask, complies with the OpenAPI specification, and offers a REST API for seamless integration with other NFDI4Chem services. Additionally, the entire system is packaged within a Docker image⁶ for effortless deployment, accompanied by a Helm chart⁷ to facilitate streamlined deployment in Kubernetes environments.

During the development of the converter service modules, some issues were identified with the ProteoWizard⁸ and BioContainer-OpenMS⁹ containers. Solutions to these issues were submitted via a GitHub pull request^{10,11}, which has been successfully merged.

⁶ Mass Spectrometry File Converter, *mass_spectrometry_file_converter*, Docker image, Docker Hub, URL: https://hub.docker.com/r/lincoln1010/mass_spectrometry_file_converter.

⁷ Converter Service Mass Spectrometry Converter Helmchart, *cs-ms-converter* in NFDI4Chem helm-charts, Github Repository, URL: <https://github.com/NFDI4Chem/helm-charts>.

⁸ ProteoWizard / containers, Github, URL: <https://github.com/ProteoWizard/container>.

⁹ Github BioContainers / containers,, OpenMS, Github, URL: <https://github.com/BioContainers/containers>.

¹⁰ Update Dockerfile, Lincoln Sherpa, Pull request, Github, URL: <https://github.com/ProteoWizard/container/pull/23>.

¹¹ Update Dockerfile of the OpenMS, Lincoln Sherpa, Issue, Github URL: <https://github.com/BioContainers/containers/pull/524>.

In addition documentation for the converter service has been created and is available via a [GitHub page](#)¹².

Figure 4: Summary report of Validation step from MS Converter Repository, cs-ms-converter. Again, validation failed for all files from the MAT 95XP instruments.

Adaptation of work plan

This deliverable has been renamed to “NFDI4Chem Converter Service Infrastructure” and combines the original two deliverables namely: “Published libraries on code hosting repository” and “Published software on code hosting repository”. Hosting the demonstration instance¹³ at TU Dresden was added on top of the original plans.

Next steps

Referring to the NFDI4Chem vision¹⁻², several key points have been identified, outlined below, which will form the basis for most of the upcoming activities and future developments

- Seamlessly incorporate the converter functionality with the Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN) Chemotion ELN, Chemotion Repository and further core repositories of NFDI4Chem.
- Implement necessary modifications to the existing code to align with user and service requirements.
- Extend the converter and validation processes to accommodate additional data types of chemistry data, such as NMR data.
- Addition of more converters to the NFDI4Chem Converter Service¹³

¹² NFDI4Chem Converter service Documentation, NFDI4Chem, URL: <https://nfdi4chem.github.io/cs-documentation/>.

¹³ NFDI4Chem Converter Service- Demonstration-Instance: <https://nfdi4chem-msconverter.zih.tu-dresden.de/api-docs#> .